

Feeding the melting pot: agroecological urbanism for inclusive and sustainable food practices

Conference proceedings of the:
10th annual Conference of the AESOP
Sustainable Food Planning group

Almere, 19-22 October

AERES University of Applied Sciences | Wageningen University & Research

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Introduction

The AESOP Sustainable Food Planning conference took place in Almere, the Netherlands, from the 19th until the 22nd of October 2022. The title of the conference was '*Feeding the melting pot: agroecological urbanism for inclusive and sustainable food practices*'. As organizers of this conference, thinking back fills us with pleasure, pride and lots of fond memories. The AERES building, light and full of plants, offered a pleasant atmosphere in which we spent two days learning and gaining insights from numerous oral presentations in parallel sessions, but also from poster discussions, keynote speeches, book presentations, deliberations in the AESOP sustainable food planning community, a policy get-together, and of course all the informal conversations enjoyed over coffee, lunch, dinner and wine. We thank all participants for making this conference work, as we really enjoyed the great atmosphere, the lively conversations and the general enthusiasm for, interest in and expertise on the conference's topics.

These conference proceedings are organised as follows: the following four sections contain the short papers belonging to the four tracks that made up the conference (social inclusion; urban agriculture; urban planning, design and development; food governance). The last section consists of the abstracts of the book and poster presentations, a short report on the YAP workshop held at the first day of the conference, and a short report on the excursion organised at the last conference day.

We trust that you will enjoy reading the papers collected in this document as much as we have, and that they bring you back to this inspiring conference.

With regards,

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Overcoming urban issues through urban agriculture

Key benefits and some possible unwanted effects

Gottero E., Cassatella C.¹

Abstract – The benefits of Urban Agriculture (UA) are manifold and concern different spheres of urban sustainability. If properly addressed, UA can contribute significantly to the achievement of the main goals of urban agendas. In this paper the authors present an overview of the key benefits and unwanted effects of UA, including tools to evaluate them, the main relationships with different UA forms, as well as how UA can address many urban policy themes.¹

Keywords – urban agriculture, benefits, unwanted effects, urban policy agenda

INTRODUCTION

Several scholars from various scientific fields claim that Urban Agriculture (UA) can address many urban policy themes and policy targets. Understanding how to encourage and support decision makers to promote and sustain UA (in order to overcome some city-related issues) is crucial for urban planning. According to recent literature, the benefits of agriculture in the urban and peri-urban areas are manifold and concern social, environmental and economic spheres. This topic has been extensively discussed, especially in the fields of urban sustainability (Feola et al., 2020; Langemeyer et al., 2021; Tapia, et al., 2021; Vásquez-Moreno & Córdova, 2013), agroecosystem services and disservices (Zabala et al., 2021), multifunctionality (Jansma et al., 2015) and governance of UA (Provè, 2018). The benefits of UA have also been partially addressed in previous research projects such as the COST Action UAE² and the UPAU study on UA³. However, a systematic and comprehensive analysis and overview of the potential benefits of UA that also includes any undesirable effects, is lacking. In addition, how to evaluate these benefits and what benefits are produced by the various types of UA, are frequently overlooked issues. In this paper the authors present some results of the research carried out in the context of “European Forum on Urban Agriculture (EFUA)” funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme⁴. The aim of this paper is to identify not only the main benefits, but also possible disservices of UA related to the environmental, social, economic, health, well-being and food domain. The relationship between different UA forms and benefits,

with respect to primary urban policy targets is also emphasized.

In order to achieve these goals, the second section of this paper explains the approach and methods that the author used, as well as the material and data collection and analysis processes. The third section presents the results of the research and describes the major findings, including the key benefits and major unwanted effects, how these benefits are monitored and assessed, as well as the relationships between UA typologies and their related benefits. In the last section, the authors explain how to interpret these results and the significance of the work, in particular in terms of the lessons learned for urban policy makers.

METHODS

UA is a varied and complex phenomenon which takes several forms, including professional urban and peri-urban farming, urban gardening and not professional agricultural activities. In order to capture various dimensions of UA, we identified, classified and systematized benefits not as compartments, but as overlaps and connections between different categories and typologies. Based on the initial unstructured literature review, previous research projects and the consultation of the partners involved in the EFUA project, we considered five potential dimensions of UA benefits: socio-cultural, environmental and climate, food, health and well-being, and economic.

We subsequently conducted a systematic literature review and project review that produced a comprehensive list of UA benefits, potential unwanted effects and indicators. This process included a search with the Scopus database, some records identified through partner suggestions and through CORDIS and the EU database search. The systematic review process was based on 17 queries and a list of key words that combined for example “Urban Agriculture” together with the terms “benefit” or “indicator” or “unwanted effects”. In order to answer the research questions and identify the main benefits of UA, we also conducted 15 interviews⁵ with stakeholders (mainly decision-makers and experts), and two online surveys⁶. The first focused on the main benefits of

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² Urban Agriculture Europe. See: Lohrberg et al., 2016.

³ Policy Department for Structural and Cohesion Policies of Directorate General for Internal Policies of the Union (2018): Research for AGRI

Committee - Urban and Peri-urban Agriculture in the EU. PE 617.468. See: Piorr et al., 2018

⁴ See: Cassatella and Gottero, 2022.

⁵ The interviews were carried out in close cooperation with Wageningen University (WU).

⁶ The first survey was carried out by WU and Wageningen Research (WR).

specific UA initiatives. Instead, the second survey contained a section for city officials and a section for experts. It mainly concerned the categories of benefits and unwanted effects at city level, indicators or sets of indicators to assess the UA benefits, urban demands which can be addressed through UA and the importance given to each type of benefit resulting from UA initiatives (based on those selected by the entire review process).

MAIN RESULTS

General findings

After a screening phase, that also included the classification of 57 papers and 29 research projects, the review process produced a list of UA benefits and unwanted effects. It collected 37 benefits and 15 unwanted effects, more than half of the benefits relate to the social and environmental sphere. Some of these benefits are inter-related and sometimes produce trade-offs.

The first on line questionnaire involved 106 responses, while the second survey produced 75. Both confirmed that the most widespread and popular benefits were socio-cultural and environmental-climate dimensions. In addition both on line questionnaires showed that urban food gardening initiatives were more likely to create social, and health and well-being benefits. In the urban farming types, social, environmental and nutritional benefits prevailed.

Key benefits

According to the stakeholders and survey participants, some of the benefits identified in the previous list through the review process were more recognisable and widespread than others. Interviews and online questionnaires allowed us to identify the key benefits for each domain (table 1).

Table 1. Key benefits of UA (Source: Cassatella and Gottero, 2022)

Benefits category	Benefits
Socio-cultural	Improvement of social cohesion and developing feelings of belonging and a sense-of-place
	Development of education, knowledge, innovation and awareness on food, agriculture and environment
	Improvement of leisure, recreation activities and tourist attractions
Environment and climate	Reduction of the urban heat island effect
	Increased quality and quantity of urban green spaces and green infrastructures
	Preservation of urban biodiversity
Food	Improvement of food security
	Improvement of food quality
Health and well-being	Improvement of physical and mental health
Economic	Improved local economies
	Creation of job opportunities

According to the literature, UA can contribute to improve social inclusion and the involvement of socio-cultural vulnerable groups, especially in the use of public spaces (Provè, 2018; Sanyé-Mengual et al., 2018). Urban gardening can also be useful to develop

feelings of belonging and a sense of place or community (Veen, 2015). The development of education and knowledge, particularly on the relationship between food, agriculture and environment, is another benefit produced by different forms of UA, especially social farms and community gardens (Artmann & Sartison, 2018). Urban farming and gardening can contribute to improved leisure, recreation activities and strengthened ecotourism (Giacchè et al., 2021; Kingsley et al., 2021).

The literature review also highlighted that UA makes a major contribution to the environment and climate by reducing the urban heat island effect and by increasing the quality and quantity of urban green spaces and green infrastructures (Gómez-Villarino & Ruiz-Garcia, 2021; Kirby et al., 2021; Langemeyer, et al., 2021; Provè, 2018). Organic or environmentally-friendly farming can also maintain urban biodiversity (Gómez-Villarino & Ruiz-Garcia, 2021; Kirby et al., 2021; Martin et al., 2016). Furthermore UA addresses food insecurity, as well as giving access to quality, fresh and healthy food (Artmann & Sartison, 2018; Kingsley et al., 2009; Kirby et al., 2021; Specht et al., 2014), especially through local farms, organic and/or traditional production systems or high-tech farming. Urban food gardening can improve physical and mental health of gardeners and practitioners (Kingsley, et al., 2009; Martin et al., 2016; Provè, 2018; Sanyé-Mengual et al., 2018). Finally, Urban oriented farming can support and develop local economies and create job opportunities (Provè, 2018; Sanyé-Mengual et al., 2018).

Main potential unwanted effects

Few scholars have conducted studies on the possible undesirable effects of UA initiatives. This research highlighted that gentrification is a potential risk. According to recent literature (Aptekar & Myers, 2020; Artmann & Sartison, 2018) and many survey respondents, some urban gardens can fuel social conflicts, race and/or class-based disparities, and increase social exclusion. The introduction of alien and invasive species is a heavily discussed risk of UA practices for the environment, especially due to horticulture and urban forest initiatives (Escobedo et al., 2011; von Döhren & Haase, 2015). It was also one of the most recognized risks in our survey.

How are these benefits monitored and assessed?

The literature and research projects review identified 230 indicators for the evaluation of the main UA benefits and unwanted effects. Indicators were collected in a list concerning mainly environmental-climate and socio-cultural dimensions. Starting from this list, we selected a set of key performance indicators, in order to represent the most important categories of benefits and typologies, as well as to consider the results of previous steps (table 2). It was created mainly for decision makers, and includes 16 state and impact indicators.

Table 2. The set of key performance indicators to assess UA benefits (Source: Cassatella and Gottero, 2022)

Benefits category	Indicators
Socio-cultural	Participation rate in UA initiatives
	Number of educational and/or participatory activities
	Number of school-gardening initiatives
	Recreational value of blue-green spaces
Environment and climate	Gentrification
	Urban Heat Island index
	Ratio of open spaces to built form
	Land use change and green space configuration
Food	Increased biodiversity
	Number of invasive alien species
Health and well-being	Food production and demand
	Local and organic food
Economic	Physical and mental impact of UA
	Local economic development
	New businesses created
	Number of new jobs created

Which UA types produce the most benefits and how to communicate them?

All types of UA produce benefits. In order to understand and highlight the relationship between the different forms of UA - such as urban farms, community gardens/parks, social farms, zero acreage farms, as well as DIY gardens⁷ - and benefits, we used evidence and expert opinion. Generally speaking, DiY and community gardens seem to achieve more socio-cultural and environmental benefits (fig. 1). In nutritional terms UA forms such as zero acreage farms and DiY gardens/farms appear more likely to produce food-related benefits. The economic sphere is mainly involved in professional farming such as zero acreage farms and urban farms (fig. 2). Finally, the UA types that produce the most health and well-being benefits are DiY and community gardens, as well as social farms. In order to highlight the main benefits of UA typologies, we collected a number of UA practices connected to each category and produced 5 “benefits leaflets” that contain a brief description of the key benefits and the main issues for attention when planning these UA initiatives.

Figure 1 – Orti Generali, a community garden in the south area of Turin (Italy) (photo by Umberto Costamagna). A good example of a nature-based solution and regeneration of degraded areas that produced environmental and socio-cultural benefits.

Figure 2 – The Milan Agricultural South Park (Italy) (photo by Giacomo Pettenati). In this peri-urban area the Consorzio DAM involves many farms that feed the urban area by producing different local agri-food products, sold directly on-farm or at retail.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

General remarks

In conclusion, the research confirmed that there is a lot of evidence which supports the benefits of UA, but some fields have yet to be fully explored. Some dimensions of the benefits, such as food, heritage domain, health and well-being, as well as quantitative analysis on measured benefits require further studies. In the literature, approaches based on perceived benefits and unmeasured benefits prevail. Finally, studies on the unwanted effects of UA are less prevalent than others and require more attention.

Lessons learned: how and which urban policy targets can the benefits of UA help to achieve?

Understanding which urban demands and urban policy themes can be addressed through UA is a crucial issue in the definition of targeted policy recommendations and supporting policy makers. This research showed that the benefits of UA can contribute to achieving some specific policy targets of European Urban Agenda. Figure 3 summarizes these relationships. As can be seen, the benefits of UA initiatives in the socio-cultural sphere can contribute to tackling social inequalities, making the city inclusive, improving the value of recreation and creating learning about UA initiatives, in urban and peri-urban areas. UA practices, including professional and not professional forms, can green the city, by contrasting land consumption and soil sealing, maintaining green spaces and the urban biodiversity. Local urban and peri-urban farms, short supply chains promoted by UA initiatives, as well as greening practices and plants related to UA, can favour the reduction of the food carbon footprint and urban heat island effect, which further contributes to climate mitigation. Feeding the city and improving quality of food are other urban issues that UA can contribute to, not only by increasing food production but also by offering wider diet opportunities. Furthermore, the quality of life, mental and physical health of citizens and well being in urban areas can be improved, especially through different forms of urban gardening

⁷ These typologies were defined by task 3.1 of EFUA project (see: Jansma et al., 2021).

such as community gardens and DIY gardens. In economic terms, urban farming can offer new opportunities for local employment and strengthen local economies, especially by connecting producers and consumers.

Figure 3. Possible contributions of UA benefits for urban policies (Source: Cassatella and Gottero, 2022).

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